

Correlation of Web-Based Learning Media to Students' Knowledge in Kala II Time of Childbirth Diii Midwifery

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ABSTRACT

The advantages offered by computer and internet technology are not only in the speed of obtaining the information that has been provided but also in multimedia facilities that can make learning more interesting, visual, interactive and fun so that it will foster students' motivation and interest in learning. This study aims to determine the relationship between web-based learning media and knowledge of the second stage of labor in DIII midwifery students. This study used an analytic descriptive method with a cross sectional design. The population in this study The population in this study were all female D-III Midwifery Institute of Bone Science and Health. The number of samples in this study amounted to 32 people with a sampling technique using non-probability sampling with purposive sampling technique. From the results of the analysis using the chi square test. The results of the research on the relationship of web-based learning media to knowledge of the second stage of labor are classified as good, as evidenced by the results of the questionnaire distributed to 32 respondents. The average score calculation of the questionnaire is 87. 18 which are categorized as good. there is a relationship between web-based learning media on knowledge of the second stage of labor in DIII midwifery students indicated by the presence of t count > t table (0.480 > 0.297) and a significance of 0.01 < 0.05, so that Ha is accepted and Ho is rejected.

KEYWORDS: Web Learning, Kala II, Childbirth, Midwifery Student

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INTRODUCTION

The use of media in learning also provides benefits, namely: 1) Learning will attract more students' attention so that it can foster learning motivation. 2) Learning materials will have a clearer meaning so that they can be better understood by students and enable students to master learning objectives better. 3) Learning methods will be more varied, not merely verbal communication through the teacher's words, so that students don't get bored and the teacher doesn't run out of steam, especially if the teacher teaches for every lesson. 4) Students do more learning activities, because they not only listen to the teacher's explanation, but also other activities such as observing, doing, demonstrating and others (Asnawir and Usman, 2002; Sudjana and Rivai, 2010).

One of the uses of technology in education is the use of the internet. The benefits of the internet as one of the largest media in the world can be used as a driving force for the advancement of educational technology in Indonesia through learning media packaged in the form of a website. For education there are many benefits of the internet that can

be obtained, especially as a learning medium. The more advanced internet-based information technology makes it easy for students to get learning material, either directly or indirectly. Learning technology appears along with the times. If in the past learning only relied on the presence of teachers and students, in this era of mobile internet technology advances, learning technology is indispensable. The advantages offered by computer and internet technology are not only in the speed of obtaining the information that has been provided but also in multimedia facilities that can make learning more interesting, visual, interactive and fun so that it will foster students' motivation and interest in learning. (Mukhtar and Iskandar, 2010; Januarisman and Ghufron, 2016; Sari and Suswanto, 2017).

Midwifery care for mothers giving birth is one of the main competencies of midwives, therefore midwives are expected to carry out their duties in a professional and quality manner with mastery of knowledge and skills, responsive to problems, able to meet the needs of mothers and babies. Having midwifery care skills can optimize high-risk detection by providing clean and safe delivery care services at every

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stage of labour. (Yulita and Juwita, 2019; Anggraini, et al, 2019; Verney, 2006).

The Askeb II course in childbirth consists of stages I-IV which teach about normal childbirth care which is a provision for students to take part in field study practices. The goal of normal delivery care is to maintain survival and provide a high degree of health for the mother and baby, through integrated and complete efforts but with minimal intervention so that the principles of safety and quality of service can be maintained at the desired level.(varney, 2010; Jnpk-kr, 2012; Nugroho, 2012)

The survey conducted by the researchers found that on several campuses in Bone Regency, namely 65% of students had difficulty memorizing study guides/work procedures, then the lack of student preparation before carrying out practicum became an obstacle, therefore students must understand the concept, know the tools and materials used along with its function, so careful preparation before entering the Laboratory is very important, as is the case now with lecturers guiding students with face-to-face tutorials with a ratio of 1:10 which takes quite a long time, mentors have limited time making it difficult to give assessments to students.

The independence of student learning, namely the extent to which in the learning process the student can participate in determining the goals, materials and learning experiences, as well as the evaluation of learning. Because this learning independence can affect student learning outcomes (Thoken 2014).

According to research conducted by Muridah Wiryanti which was conducted in 2020, the results of her research show that there is an effect of learning carried out using web-based media on improving practicum skills for the

second stage of labor. If this problem is not resolved immediately, it is likely to have an impact a big impact on student learning outcomes.

Based on the problems described above, it is necessary to conduct research on the relationship of web-based learning media to knowledge of the second stage of midwifery DIII students.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was conducted at the Bone Science and Health Institute. The type of research used is quantitative research methods. The population in this study were all female students of the Bone Science and Health Institute for the 2022-2023 academic year. A sample of 32 people were taken using a purposive sampling technique and who were willing to take part in this study by signing an informed consent.

Data collection was carried out by researchers using primary data obtained directly from respondents using questionnaires and surveys via Google forms and data obtained from the Bone Institute of Science and Health regarding the number of female students and the value of midwifery care. The data analysis technique was Descriptive Statistics. The collected data were analyzed using the Statistical Package For Social Science (SPSS) program for windows, in stages consisting of the average value and value categories as well as the results of the survey. the steps taken in this research is to calculate the acquisition score of each indicator. After that, calculating the percentage of answers from each indicator then obtained the percentage results for each indicator, then the researcher drew conclusions from the research results (Sugiono 2011).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1: Frequency Distribution of D-III Midwifery Students at the Institute of Science and Health Bones 2022-2023

Characteristics	Group		total n (%)	p=value*
	Control (16)	Intervention (16)		
Age				
18 years	6(33.3%)	7 (46.7%)	13 (40.0%)	0.300
19 years	10 (66.7%)	9 (53.3%)	19 (60.0%)	
old				
GPA				
Not enough	0 (0.0%)	2 (6.7%)	2 (3.3%)	-
Good	16 (100.0%)	14 (93.3%)	16 (100.0%)	

*Hogeneity of Variance Test

Based on table 4.1, it shows that the age characteristic variance in the control group and the application group is

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relatively the same (homogeneous), the majority are ≤ 19 years old in both groups. The GPA variance did not appear because there were no respondents with less GPA in the

control group, although almost all respondents had a good GPA > 3.00 in both the control and application groups.

Table 4.3: Differences in Knowledge of Care for the Second Stage of Childbirth before and after giving Learning Media to female midwifery students at the Bone Science and Health Institute in 2022-2023.

Skills Section	Pre-post	n	p-value*
Recognizing Signs and Symptoms	Decrease	0	1,000
	Increase	0	
	Stay	16	
Preparing for Help	Decrease	2	0.739
	Increase	2	
	Stay	12	
Ensuring Complete Dilation and State of the Fetus	Decrease	1	0.206
	Increase	3	
	Stay	12	
Preparing Mother and Family	Decrease	2	0.705
	Increase	1	
	Stay	13	
Preparation for Childbirth	Decrease	3	0.366
	Increase	3	
	Stay	10	
Childbirth Assistance	Decrease	0	0.002
	Increase	7	
	Stay	9	

*Wilcoxon test

Based on table 4.3, it shows that the skills section that differed significantly before and after learning conventional media was only section 6 (Aid in childbirth) which showed a minority of skills increased. The 5 skill sections showed that there were differences between pre and post but not significant, the majority of skill scores remained pre to post.

DISCUSSION

In table 4.5 it shows that in the control group there are differences in skills in measurements I and II but not too significant the value of $\rho = 1,000 >$ of $\alpha = 0.05$, this means that H_0 is accepted, so it can be said that there is a relationship with the provision of conventional learning media. The skills section that differed significantly before and after learning conventional media was only section 6 (Aid in childbirth) which showed an increase in skills in the minority. The 5 skill sections showed that there were differences between pre and post but not significant, the majority of skill scores remained pre to post. The results of this study are in line with those conducted by Muridah Wiriyanti which was conducted in 2020 showing that in the control group there was no difference in skills in measurements I and II with a p value < 1.000 contributes 46.3%, however in part 2 (Recognizing the symptoms of the second stage), there is a significant difference in the scores of measurements I and II. It can be seen from the increase in the score of the respondents in that section. This is in line with research conducted by (Kodiyah

et al., 2017) material without using media, students tend to be bored and not interested in attending lectures, while providing learning media in the form of videos and animations students will be more motivated to follow learning.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis, the researchers assume that this is the future reference so that they can utilize technology so as to further improve practicum skills, especially in the second stage of labor care. It can be concluded that the use of WEB-based learning media is good for improving student skills in carrying out midwifery care, especially during the second stage of labor. In line with the results of research conducted by (Lisa, Hernowo and Anwar, 2019) shows that there are significant differences in delivery care skills in providing web-based learning media with conventional learning media.

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